

Zinc Oxide Nanowires for Biosensing Applications

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Abstract — In this work, we demonstrate the immobilization of carboxylic acid moieties on the surface of ZnO nanowires and its potential for biosensing applications. ZnO nanowires were synthesized via Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) technique and appropriately characterized. Vibrational spectroscopic techniques were used to determine nature of bonding and orientation of oleic acid molecule at nanowire surface, which is used as model system. Furthermore, on the basis of photoluminescence data on modified- and unmodified ZnO nanowires with oleic acid, a generic approach to sense biomolecules along with mechanism of sensing is proposed.

Index Terms – ZnO nanowires, CVD, Biosensor, Spectroscopy, Functionalization

I. INTRODUCTION

ZnO nanowires have attracted persistent attention for numerous applications such as chemical sensing, optoelectronics and biomolecule detection [1-5]. Owing to their one-dimensional (1D) nature, these nanostructures offer high sensitivity and real time detection. ZnO nanowires are of particular interest for sensing applications due to their wide band gap (3.37 eV) and high exciton binding energy (60 meV) which broadens the scope of detection from purely resistive [6] or FET-based detection [7] to less complex optical methods. The diameter of these nanowires being comparable to biological molecules to be sensed and high surface-to-volume ratio increases the sensitivity of detection manifolds [8]. Combined with their superior optical and electrical properties, ZnO nanowires can serve as excellent transducers which can be interfaced with macroscopic instruments. In addition to these properties, ZnO nanowires have an additional advantage in terms of being biocompatible which make them a lucrative candidate for *in vivo* biological applications. Based on previous empirical evidence it has been established that 1D semiconductor surfaces have active sites which can be easily immobilized with numerous biomolecules [9, 10]. Contrary to other non-oxide semiconducting materials, whose surface activity gets reduced due to native oxide formation, ZnO nanowire surface is resistant to surface passivation due to inherent presence of oxygen atoms on nanowire surface lattice sites. In fact, the resistive and FET-based detection of chemical and biological species is based on electrical conductivity changes due to complex formation of different chemical species on nanowire surface with oxygen vacancies and other lattice defects. Despite the promising electrical, optical and surface characteristics there have been few reports on use of ZnO nanowires for biological sensing of complex molecules as compared to nanoparticles and films [11, 12].

Previous investigations with ZnO nanoparticles and films functionalized with thiols, silanes etc. [13, 14] have shown great promise for different applications. In one of our previous work we confirmed chemical interaction between oleic acid and ZnO nanowires [15].

However, to effectively engineer the surface of ZnO nanowires for biological sensing of carboxylic acid moieties such as amino acids, an in-depth understanding of surface phenomenon and interactions is crucial. Therefore, in this work we demonstrate immobilization of oleic acid molecules on ZnO nanowire surface and investigate local bonding environment and orientation of oleic acid molecules. Oleic acid is a surfactant which has been shown to attract different moieties present in biologically important molecules [16]. It is believed that modifying ZnO nanowire surface with oleic acid can improve detection limits of these moieties to molecular level. The schematic for the idea is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic representation for nanowire based detection

Hence, in this work we synthesized ZnO nanowires in a customized CVD furnace and established the morphology and composition of the synthesized nanowires through SEM, TEM and X-Ray diffraction. Thereafter, the ZnO nanowires were modified with oleic acid and the nature of bonding and surface orientation of oleic acid molecules on nanowire surface was determined with surface sensitive characterization techniques of Raman and Infrared Spectroscopy. Photoluminescence measurements on modified- and unmodified- ZnO nanowires showed changes in peak heights based on which a prospective mechanism of sensing oleic acid on ZnO nanowire surface is proposed.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The ZnO nanowires were synthesized on ZnO (001) substrate using VLS mechanism widely published in literature [17, 18]. In brief, ZnO substrates were coated with gold (4 nm) by sputtering (Shirley Sputtering System) which serves a template for the growth of ZnO nanowires during

the VLS process. Precursor powders of ZnO (99.9%, from J.T. Baker) and graphite (99%, from Alfa Aesar) were homogeneously mixed in 1:1 ratio and introduced in a customized CVD furnace at 950°C. Mixed gas (2% O₂+Ar) was utilized as a carrier medium. Using optimal flow rate and growth time of 30 min, dense nanowire growth was observed. The morphology and crystal structure of the synthesized nanowires were determined by FE-SEM (JEOL 7000), X-Ray Diffraction (Bruker-AXS) and TEM (Technai). After characterization, the ZnO nanowires as-synthesized on ZnO substrate were dipped in oleic acid solution (1% v/v in Hexane) for 15 mins to functionalize ZnO nanowire surface. Thereafter, the specimens were copiously rinsed in pure hexane to remove unadsorbed oleic acid. It is essential to remove unadsorbed oleic acid to prevent erroneous signal generation during subsequent characterization. Nature of bonding and orientation of oleic acid on nanowire surface were determined by comparing unmodified- and modified-ZnO nanowires through Raman (Jobin Yvon, HR800 UV) and Fourier Transform-Infrared spectroscopy. Subsequently, the photoluminescence spectrum of unmodified- and modified- ZnO nanowires were obtained using spectrophotometer (FluoroMax-3, Jobin Yvon) in a 1cm quartz cuvette transparent to UV radiation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1(a) and 1(b) show the SEM images of ZnO nanowires on ZnO substrate along with X-Ray diffraction (XRD) spectrum of the nanowires, as synthesized by the CVD process. It can be observed that the nanowires are vertically aligned with respect to substrate and are laterally branched close to the tip. While the vertical alignment is due to absence of lattice mismatch between the nanowires and the substrate, hierarchical growth could be due to high supersaturation of Zn vapors in the furnace as suggested by Zhang et al. [19].

Figure 1: (a) Tilted and; (b) top view of ZnO nanowires synthesized on ZnO substrate; (c) XRD spectrum of nanowires showing preferential c-axis growth

Figure 1(c) corresponds to XRD spectrum of the as-synthesized ZnO nanowires which indicates preferential growth along [0001] direction as the (001) peak is sufficiently high in intensity than other peaks, consistent with documented literature. In addition, hexagonal wurtzite structure of the synthesized nanowires can be confirmed by superimposition of standard spectra (ICDD PDF# 01-089-0510) over the obtained spectrum. This observation can be further supported by TEM analysis of the nanowires as presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: (a) TEM image of as-synthesized ZnO NW; (b) HR-TEM image showing [0001] growth direction of NW

After establishing the morphology and crystal structure, the as-synthesized nanowires were functionalized with oleic acid as described in the experimental section. Surface analysis and characterization were appropriately carried out through surface sensitive techniques of Raman spectroscopy and FT-IR. Figure 3(a) shows the Raman spectrum of the as-synthesized ZnO nanowires. The characteristic ZnO peaks were observed at 439 cm⁻¹ (E₂ mode) and 580 cm⁻¹ (A_{1(LO)} mode), which serve as reference to further modification procedures [20].

Figure 3: (a) Raman spectrum of as-synthesized ZnO nanowires; (b) Raman spectrum of modified-ZnO nanowires

Figure 3(b) is the Raman spectrum of the oleic acid-modified ZnO nanowires. It can be seen that the spectrum

has peaks corresponding to oleic acid in addition to characteristic ZnO peaks. This observation is suggestive of possible modification of nanowire surface by oleic acid, but nature of carboxylate bonding is ambiguous. Accordingly, complementary evidence was obtained through FT-IR. Figure 4(a) is the FT-IR spectrum of 1% oleic acid (v/v) in hexane. Peaks at 937 cm^{-1} and 1464 cm^{-1} correspond to out-of-plane and in-plane OH deformations respectively. Broad peak at 1284 cm^{-1} can be attributed to C-O stretch, while the intense peak at 1710 cm^{-1} is C=O. Small peaks at 2570 cm^{-1} and 2673 cm^{-1} indicate oleic acid dimer formation. The group of peaks from 2825 cm^{-1} - 2950 cm^{-1} are from CH_2 and CH_3 asymmetric and symmetric vibrations stretches and are typical of long chain organic compounds. Weak peak at 3005 cm^{-1} is the C-H stretch of (*cis*)-alkene [21]. Figure 4(b) shows the modified-ZnO nanowires spectrum. It can be observed that the changes in spectrum are primarily due to features associated with carboxylic acid group, leading to bound carboxylate. The absence of peaks at 2570 cm^{-1} and 2673 cm^{-1} rule out any possibility of oleic acid dimerization. It can also be observed that C=O band at 1710 cm^{-1} , C-O stretch at 1284 cm^{-1} and the out-of-plane O-H deformation mode is no longer present. Instead, new features indicative of carboxylate species appear. Peaks at 1407 cm^{-1} and 1589 cm^{-1} can be attributed to COO^- symmetric and asymmetric stretching respectively. Remaining unidentified peaks are characteristic to long hydrocarbon chain as mentioned before. All peaks beyond 2800 cm^{-1} , associated with CH_3 and CH_2 as well as C=C modes beyond 2800 cm^{-1} remain in same position pre- and post-modification of ZnO nanowires with oleic acid.

Figure 4: FT-IR spectra of (a) oleic acid 1% (v/v) in Hexane; (b) oleic acid modified ZnO nanowires

After immobilization of oleic acid molecules on ZnO nanowires surface, we tested the photoluminescence (PL) behaviour of unmodified- and modified-ZnO nanowires. Figure 5(a) shows the PL spectrum of as-synthesized nanowires. Weak peaks at 510 nm and 536 nm can be attributed to defect related emission and prominent peaks at 360 nm and 380 nm are due to onset of excitonic band-edge related emission. When the nanowire surface sites are

occupied with oleic acid molecules, two significant changes occur in the spectrum. In figure 5(b) the defect related peaks disappear which could be due to occupation of surface sites by oxygen from oleic acid, which otherwise would have contributed to visible luminescence. Furthermore, the band-edge related emission peaks merge and display a slight red-shift which can be attributed to surface adsorption of oleic acid molecules. Both these effects could be due to surface interaction between ZnO nanowire and oxygen atoms from oleic acid. Although, the role of oxygen in ZnO PL is still debated, it can nonetheless serve as a functional tool for quantification and characterization.

Figure 5: (a) PL spectrum of as-synthesized ZnO NWs; (b) PL spectrum of modified ZnO NWs

For developing biosensors based on ZnO nanowires, emission characteristics, both band-edge and defect related together, can serve as a fingerprint to identify different biological moieties.

III. CONCLUSIONS

ZnO nanowires synthesized in a customized CVD furnace were functionalized with oleic acid. After appropriate characterization of the as-synthesized nanowires by FE-SEM, TEM and X-Ray diffraction, the surface binding and nature of bonded species was investigated through surface sensitive techniques of Raman and Infrared spectroscopy. Based on data obtained it was determined that oleic acid binds to ZnO nanowire surface through carboxylic acid moiety, as the C=O peak in IR spectra of modified- ZnO nanowires was no longer present. PL spectrum of unmodified- and modified- ZnO nanowires showed changes in defect related emission intensity as well as near-band edge emission intensity. Together, they could be a means to identify different biological species with high accuracy and sensitivity. Nonetheless, surface engineering and analysis of ZnO nanowire surface plays a crucial role to develop high quality nanosensors for different sensing applications including biological sensing.

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